

Annick Paternoster. *Historical Etiquette: Etiquette Books in Nineteenth-Century Western Cultures.* 2022. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.

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This is a rich, innovative, and significant book. It makes substantial advances in our understanding of nineteenth-century politeness from a previously unexplored perspective, namely etiquette, whose prominence spanned over an entire century. But what makes this book even more valuable is the methodology employed, because to undertake such a comprehensive study, the author integrates multiple approaches to propose a multi-disciplinary theoretical framework for reflection. The author also considers the needs of newcomers to this rapidly growing field, offering an accessible book that references numerous relevant works.

Usually, the phenomenon of politeness in Western culture resists traditional chronologies, but this is not the case with etiquette, which essentially developed after the Napoleonic Wars, reached its zenith in the second half of the nineteenth century, and declined after the First World War. Throughout this period, etiquette was a widespread phenomenon in every Western country, and a notable strength of this study is its panoramic scope, encompassing Great Britain, France, Italy, the Netherlands and the United States. It effectively demonstrates the universal nature of etiquette whilst offering insightful explanations of some of its cultural specificities. The author also succeeds in proving that there is a real interest in tackling the late modern period, which remains under-represented in historical pragmatics.

The book is organised into eight chapters, which follow one another in a clear and logical sequence, with coherence further supported by the introductions and conclusions of each chapter and a system of infra-textual cross-references. The consistency of the whole is also maintained through the gradual construction of a definition of historical etiquette, which is refined and expanded as the study progresses. Moreover, etiquette is not solely examined as a phenomenon confined to the past: both the introduction (Chapter 1) and conclusion (Chapter 8) highlight the growing interest in etiquette today, including social, digital, business, corporate and global (international) etiquette. The book's starting point is, therefore, to look to the past as a better way of understanding the current trend towards the reformalisation of social norms (Wouters 2007). Chapter 1 presents the thesis, research objectives, and methodological approach. The aim is to establish etiquette as a functional concept within politeness theory, an area that has not previously addressed. It is conceptualised as an abstract system of politeness rooted in a specific spatio-temporal context and, according to the author, a late modern manifestation of the concept of Discernment, typically used in analyses of non-European cultures.

The objective of Chapters 2, 3 and 4 is to narrow down the research object. Chapter 2 ("Etiquette Books") examines etiquette books diachronically, distinguishing them from other instructional literature, such as courtesy books and conduct books. The primary distinction lies in their separation of manners from morals, focussing solely on enumerating and describing rules to be followed, whereas conduct books targeted at younger audiences continue to emphasise moral and religious development. In addition, etiquette books served as instruments of social mobility for the ambitious middle class, eager to enter aristocratic circles (the aristocracy of wealth in the USA). It also served as an instrument of the feminisation of etiquette in two ways: firstly, etiquette books enabled women to engage in social activities outside the home; secondly, and this was less visible, since most of the authors of these books were women, it was also a means of emancipation for them. Analysis of the material aspect of

books from all the linguacultures studied revealed a surprising consistency, particularly in terms of format, number, price, etc. This consistency justified the possibility of building the digital corpus consisting of ninety-two books of etiquette used in this study, including representative samples from books published in American English, British English and French, and a smaller selection of Italian and Dutch etiquette books.

In Chapter 3 (“Defining Etiquette”), the analysis of the introductory sections of the corpus texts provides an initial working definition of etiquette. This qualitative analysis explores the specific characteristics distinguishing etiquette from other terms (e.g., *bon ton*, *savoir-vivre* and *usages du monde* in French), and the relationship to morality as seen in conduct books. The findings suggest that etiquette was perceived as distinct from politeness, functioning as a kind of grammar of social relations, with precise laws to be followed. Paradoxically, whilst etiquette itself is an exclusionary practice intended to uphold the social hierarchy, etiquette books represent an inclusive effort to facilitate the entry into high society. The chapter’s quantitative analysis examines the term etiquette across different linguacultures, aiming to identify synonyms and collocations. The analysis highlights two key features: the hierarchical nature of etiquette and its association with formal, fixed social events such as dinners, balls and visits. The conclusiveness of this quantitative approach varies with the size of each corpus and the polysemic nature of the term etiquette in each language. In French for example, the term is rarely used, with *savoir-vivre* being more prevalent and encompassing both etiquette and politeness. Therefore, further, more detailed analysis is required to elucidate the significant distinctions between these terms.

The objective of Chapter 4 (“The Origin of Etiquette”) is to examine the presence of the term etiquette in large diachronic corpora and dictionaries. The author utilises various tools and corpora to contextualise his analysis, relating it to the evolution of politeness during the *ancien régime* and the significant changes of the twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. The spread of etiquette between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries began in Spanish courtly circles and subsequently appeared in French, Italian, Dutch, and eventually British and American English. This courtly etiquette evolved into social etiquette in the nineteenth century (Chapter 4.4), as the influence of courts diminished, or in their absence, as seen in the USA and France following the establishment of the republic. This chapter concludes the first, primarily diachronic, part of the book, and the definition developed herein is both tested and refined in the subsequent chapters.

Chapters 5, 6 and 7 form the second part of the book, which provides an in-depth analysis of key characteristics of etiquette. The primary aim is to support the hypothesis that etiquette, as a social practice, represents the manifestation of Discernment – the quasi-mandatory expression of strict adherence to the prevailing social hierarchy, appropriate to specific circumstances. This hypothesis builds on the author’s previous work (Paternoster 2019, 2023) and is inspired by Kádár and Mills (2013). Chapter 5 (“Scripts and Lines”) examines the normative and obligatory nature of etiquette by analysing the social contexts in which it occurs, such as visits, dinners, balls, conversations, greetings and letter writing. Etiquette must have been articulated in rules and laws because these behaviours could not be deduced and therefore had to be learned and internalised. The various sequences of behaviour had to be rehearsed to be memorised, as every gesture and word was significant and could influence an individual’s future prospects. This underscores the importance of scripts, which detail the expected behaviours, highlighting the high degree of conventionalisation and, therefore, the theatrical or choreographic nature of etiquette.

Given this level of complexity, the issue of blunders became crucial, and this is the focus of Chapter 6. This risk rendered every social situation a test, designed to expose intruders and subject them to embarrassment or outright ostracism. Two exemplary cases are described in greater detail: debutants and debutantes, and those who lived in the countryside who had to

demonstrate their social skills in order to join high society. However, the most despised by the high society were the upwardly mobile, or “transclasses”, who were most at risk of committing unforgivable social blunders and so desperately needed to refine their manners. They were undoubtedly the most assiduous readers of etiquette books. The author also explores rituals of social exclusion aimed at stigmatising undesirable individuals and severing their ties with the group, and then addresses remedies for the risk of blunder (Chapter 6.7), with a particular focus on ease and tact. Inherited from the Renaissance concept of “sprezzatura”, ease involved concealing the effort required to follow etiquette, making the rules appear to be second nature and seemingly innate. Tact, on the other hand, was rooted in judgment and prudence, enabling individuals to choose the appropriate course of action in social situations that were not explicitly covered by etiquette rules. Therefore, the author argues that tact can be seen as Discernment1 (Kádár and Paternoster 2015), as it requires personal judgment, whilst etiquette could be regarded as Discernment2.

Chapter 7 (“Precedence”) continues the exploration of etiquette as a form of Discernment, this time focussing on the issue of precedence embedded in the social hierarchy, which can be considered a non-verbal manifestation of Discernment. Precedence, a source of dispute for centuries, became codified in most European countries, specifying the order in which different members of a group should participate in ceremonies and social events. The privilege associated with precedence affected time (the opportunity to perform an action first) and place (seat of honour), as well as determined forms of address and the verbal and non-verbal aspects of speech acts. The chapter elaborates on several key cases of precedence: dinner precedence, often involving highly detailed seating arrangements; the precedence observed in drawing-rooms and ballrooms; and other, less commonly addressed cases, such as carriage, riding, promenade, greeting, introduction, and handshaking precedence. This section concludes with an analysis of the rules for letter writing, including the material aspects (such as the dimensions of the paper and of the blank space), which were crucial in expressing deference to superior rank. In conclusion, this characteristic also confirms, according to the author, that precedence is indeed a form of Discernment.

The book concludes with the idea that etiquette may serve as the missing link between the Discernment practices of previous eras and those of the twenty-first century. Chapter 8, which draws exclusively on British and American sources, suggests that contemporary etiquette is still shaped by historical precedents. Whilst the range of contexts requiring adherence to etiquette has narrowed, mainly to formal interactions (such as diplomatic and semi-institutional business etiquette, as well as formal dining), the discourse found in modern etiquette books and websites of etiquette training academies continues to emphasise the utility of knowing the rules to minimise embarrassment and anxiety about committing a *faux pas*, and foster genuine confidence. A notable difference today is the evolved relationship between etiquette and politeness, with greater emphasis on moral values, respect and empathy in interactions, making the emotional aspect more significant than ever.

In conclusion, this book stands out as a pioneering contribution to the study of nineteenth-century etiquette, offering a comprehensive and multi-disciplinary analysis that bridges historical and contemporary perspectives. This is due in large part to Paternoster’s extensive knowledge of both older politeness literature, as demonstrated in her previous book (Paternoster 2015), and that of the nineteenth, twentieth and even twenty-first centuries. The author’s methodological rigour and comparative approach that includes etiquette books from five distinct linguacultures provide a nuanced understanding of the social phenomenon that profoundly shaped the behaviour and interactions of that period. Moreover, this book not only elucidates the complexities of social practices in the past but also offers valuable insights into their continued relevance in modern society.

The thorough examination of historical etiquette, coupled with the accessible presentation of theories and data, makes this book an essential resource for experienced and young scholars alike. We can only hope that this significant work will encourage further exploration, especially since there is a gap that needs to be filled: there are two linguacultures not covered by the author, namely German and Spanish. This gap is understandable, as every book and researcher have their limits. However, a broader spectrum might highlight notable differences due to varying socio-cultural contexts, potentially shedding light on the fragility of this etiquette model, which failed to withstand the upheavals of the First World War. In addition, employing the same methodology could help to better highlight developments and trace the evolution of etiquette throughout the twentieth century. The book's major contribution lies in illustrating that exploring historical contexts can provide fresh insights into the resurgence of etiquette today, and that etiquette remains more relevant than the decreasing availability of books on politeness in contemporary bookstores might imply.

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